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**Evaluation of CAIRT scientific performance in Phase A
through analysis and demonstration**

Technical Report TR-1

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<p><i>Abstract</i></p> <p>Using the LPE, the performance of the two CAIRT instrument concepts has been simulated separately. For selected atmospheric parameters FL2S calculations are used for linear retrievals of the TDS-G-04 scenario.</p>		
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1 The SWB for linear performance evaluation

1.1 Overview

The linear SWB has extensively been used for requirement consolidation as described in [1]. The calculations are performed here separately for each of the expected L1b performance of Concepts A and B.

The emphasis is on predicted NESR as the prime contributor to total uncertainty. Some other system design specifications, namely SEDF and sampling, are also applied for the LPE parametric instrument model. All other L1b performances and uncertainties (i.e., beyond NESR, SEDF, and sampling) are assumed at threshold specification as described in [1].

1.2 Specification of both Concepts for instrument simulation

1.2.1 Instrument simulation

Basic parameters for simulation of CAIRT observed spectra/perturbation spectra and Jacobians from the spectra database by the instrument simulator are summarized in Table 1. All other parameters are provided in [1].

Table 1 Baseline instrument simulation parameters for Concepts A and B (only those differing from Table 5 in [1]).

Parameter	Concept A	Concept B
Observing elevation angles	Constant elevation angle difference as calculated for a 5 km tangent point (unrefracted) with 0.943 km spacing ($R_e = 6367.4445$ km, $h_{sat} = 800$ km) from 5 km to 115 km altitude.	Constant elevation angle difference as calculated for a 5 km tangent point (unrefracted) with 0.847 km spacing ($R_e = 6367.4445$ km, $h_{sat} = 800$ km) from 5 km to 115 km altitude.
SEDF (inner part)	Left part of Figure 1.	Right part of Figure 1.

1.2.2 Linear performance estimation

Linear performance estimation has been described in [1]. The uncertainties assumption applied here are different in terms of assumed spectral noise (NESR). This is illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 1 Vertical SEDFs used in instrument simulation. Left: Concept A, right: Concept B. Colored solid lines denote the Concept SEDF functions. Dotted blue lines denote the function used in the requirement consolidation [1]. Vertical black lines show the sample size height, with solid ones for the Concepts and dotted ones as used in the requirement consolidation.

Table 2 Contributions to the LPE uncertainty estimation (only those differing from Table 7 in [1]).

Parameter	Concept A	Concept B
NESR	Blue curve in Figure 2.	Orange curve in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Comparison of predicted performance for both Concepts as used in the analysis here against the NESR performance requirements.

Table 3 L2a requirement compliance categories applied to L2 performance metrics (G: goal; T: threshold requirement).

Cat.	Performance evaluation	Assessment (example: predicted [p] vs required [G/T] uncertainty u)
1	Exceeds (better than) goal	$u_p/u_G \leq 1$
2	Between goal and threshold	$u_p/u_G > 1$ and $u_p/u_T \leq 0.8$
3	Threshold compliant	$0.8 > u_p/u_T \leq 1.2$
4	Non-compliant	$u_p/u_T > 1.2$

2 CAIRT performance evaluation

2.1 Overview

Figure 6 to Figure 42 show the SWB-estimated performance for both Concepts for temperature and all target species. using the resolution and uncertainty metrics defined in Table 3. In addition to the total uncertainty, individual contributors are indicated separately, distinguishing between (i) random uncertainties due to spatially and temporarily uncorrelated errors, which can be reduced by averaging; (ii) calibration uncertainties causing systematic effects during short time intervals associated with calibration periods but behaving as random uncertainty on larger time scales; and (iii) systematic uncertainties due to spatially or temporarily correlated errors resulting in biases in the L2 products.

In addition, FL2S simulations have been performed for whole atmosphere scenes (TDS-G-04), based on the LPE performance output. Synthetic CAIRT L2a data, generated from Concept A spectra, are compared to the model “truth” in the right panels of the Figures. This comparison demonstrates e.g. the capacity of CAIRT to reproduce wave-induced small-scale features in the temperature distribution and filamentary structures in ozone. It does so even for the scenario’s strongly perturbed NH polar winter conditions, characterized by an elevated stratopause over the North pole (30 km higher than at mid-latitudes) and record-low temperatures below. Differences between CAIRT-simulated data and synthetic truth may exceed the estimated absolute uncertainty due to the contribution of so-called “smoothing” errors, since it was preferred for these comparisons not to apply averaging kernels to the model truth.

The entire performance assessment for Concept A is summarised in Figure 3 for all primary L2a targets and the L2b product NO_y. Compared against the observational requirements, L2a performance is compliant with all primary geophysical data requirements, except for night-time CO in the MLT. This is not deemed mission critical.

A summary for all L2a targets for Concept B is provided in Figure 4. As for Concept A, Concept B L2a performance is compliant with all primary geophysical data requirements, except for night-time CO in the MLT, which is not deemed mission critical.

Figure 3 Retrieval performance assessment overview plot for all primary L2a targets and NO_y, for Concept A. Left, estimated total uncertainty/error; right, spatial resolution (*hvxres*). Colours correspond to the evaluated averaged performance (over ERS and regions), against goal and threshold geophysical requirements from Table 3.

Figure 4 Same as Figure 3 but for Concept B.

2.2 Temperature

Figure 5 Left part: L2 performance estimation for temperature for Concept A considering all ERS atmospheres. Background shading corresponds to the L2a requirements (legend in Table 3). The total error is the 1σ equivalent width of an error distribution, calculated as the geometric sum of all random and systematic components assessed. Vertical resolution is $\Delta z_i / (\sum_j A_{ij,ij})$. In the horizontal resolution sub-plot, red solid lines are along-track resolution (Δy ($\sum_j A_{ij,ij} / A_{ij,ij}$)), dashed red lines across-track binning. The black line corresponds to the area-related horizontal resolution $hres = \sqrt{altres \times act}$ for which the requirements are defined. Right part: “true” temperature and emulated CAIRT data, as well as their differences, for an orbit segment across the TDS-G-04 scenario.

Figure 6 Performance estimation for temperature for Concept B. Detailed caption provided in Figure 5.

2.3 O₃

Figure 7 Performance estimation for ozone for Concept A. Detailed caption provided in Figure 5.

Figure 8 Performance estimation for ozone for Concept B. Detailed caption provided in Figure 5.

2.4 NO

Figure 9 Performance estimation for NO for Concept A. Detailed caption provided in Figure 5.

Figure 10 Performance estimation for NO for Concept B. Detailed caption provided in Figure 5.

2.5 NO₂

Figure 11 Performance estimation for NO₂ for Concept A. Detailed caption provided in Figure 5.

Figure 12 Performance estimation for NO₂ for Concept B. Detailed caption provided in Figure 5.

2.6 CO

Figure 13 Performance estimation for CO for Concept A. Detailed caption provided in Figure 5.

Figure 14 Performance estimation for CO for Concept B. Detailed caption provided in Figure 5.

2.7 H₂O

Figure 15 Performance estimation for H₂O for Concept A. Detailed caption provided in Figure 5.

Figure 16 Performance estimation for H₂O for Concept B. Detailed caption provided in Figure 5.

2.8 CH₄

Figure 17 Performance estimation for CH₄ for Concept A. Detailed caption provided in Figure 5.

Figure 18 Performance estimation for CH₄ for Concept B. Detailed caption provided in Figure 5.

2.9 N₂O

Figure 19 Performance estimation for N₂O for Concept A. Detailed caption provided in Figure 5.

Figure 20 Performance estimation for N₂O for Concept B. Detailed caption provided in Figure 5.

2.10 HNO₃

Figure 21 Performance estimation for HNO₃ for Concept A. Detailed caption provided in Figure 5.

Figure 22 Performance estimation for HNO₃ for Concept B. Detailed caption provided in Figure 5.

2.11 N₂O₅

Figure 23 Performance estimation for N₂O₅ for Concept A. Detailed caption provided in Figure 5.

Figure 24 Performance estimation for N₂O₅ for Concept B. Detailed caption provided in Figure 5.

2.12 CIONO₂

Figure 25 Performance estimation for CIONO₂ for Concept A. Detailed caption provided in Figure 5.

Figure 26 Performance estimation for CIONO₂ for Concept B. Detailed caption provided in Figure 5.

2.13 CFC-11

Figure 27 Performance estimation for CFC-11 for Concept A. Detailed caption provided in Figure 5.

Figure 28 Performance estimation for CFC-11 for Concept B. Detailed caption provided in Figure 5.

2.14 CFC-12

Figure 29 Performance estimation for CFC-12 for Concept A. Detailed caption provided in Figure 5.

Figure 30 Performance estimation for CFC-12 for Concept B. Detailed caption provided in Figure 5.

2.15 HCFC-22

Figure 31 Performance estimation for HCFC-22 for Concept A. Detailed caption provided in Figure 5.

Figure 32 Performance estimation for HCFC-22 for Concept B. Detailed caption provided in Figure 5.

2.16 SF₆

Figure 33 Performance estimation for SF₆ for Concept A. Detailed caption provided in Figure 5.

Figure 34 Performance estimation for SF₆ for Concept B. Detailed caption provided in Figure 5.

2.17 SO₂

Figure 35 Performance estimation for SO₂ for Concept A. Detailed caption provided in Figure 5.

Figure 36 Performance estimation for SO₂ for Concept B. Detailed caption provided in Figure 5.

2.18 OCS

Figure 37 Performance estimation for OCS for Concept A. Detailed caption provided in Figure 5.

Figure 38 Performance estimation for OCS for Concept B. Detailed caption provided in Figure 5.

2.19 H₂SO₄-liq

Figure 39 Performance estimation for H₂SO₄-liq for Concept A. Detailed caption provided in Figure 5.

Figure 40 Performance estimation for H₂SO₄-liq for Concept B. Detailed caption provided in Figure 5.

2.20 PAN

Figure 41 Performance estimation for PAN for Concept A. Detailed caption provided in Figure 5.

Figure 42 Performance estimation for PAN for Concept A. Detailed caption provided in Figure 5.

3 Literature

- [1] M. Höpfner, B. Funke, P. Preusse, Q. Errera, B.-M. Sinnhuber, and J. Ungermann, 'DEL-09-CAIRT-PhAPerReC-3.1 – CAIRT measurement requirements assessment - Technical Note TN-3', DEL-09-CAIRT-PhAPerReC-3.1, Nov. 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18496134>